

Public opinion survey on risks relating to food, and recognisability of the European Food Safety Authority in Slovenia

Contracting Authority: MAFF, Administration of the Republic of Slovenia for Food Safety, Veterinary Sector and Plant Protection

The project is financed by the European Union.

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I. SURVEY DESCRIPTION

Who?	<i>Slovenian residents aged 18+</i>
How many?	<i>Simple random sample: sample size n=700</i>
How?	<i>CATI; computer-assisted telephone interviewing</i>
When?	<i>September 2017</i>

In compliance with the standards recommended by the ESOMAR*, the following data must be provided when publishing the results of this report: Contractor: Aragon d.o.o.

Population captured: Slovenian citizens aged 18 and above

Sample size: Entire Slovenia; n=700

Sampling: simple random sample

Date of implementation: 14–28 September 2017

Method: CATI; computer-assisted telephone interviewing (n=700)

* ESOMAR/WAPOR Guide to Opinion Polls, ESOMAR 2003.

II. REVIEW OF MAIN FINDINGS

- A trend of growing trust in the safety of purchased food can be noticed. Half of the respondents in 2017 believe that the food they buy is safe. Only 25% of respondents in the 2013 survey were of the same opinion, and 39.4% in 2015.
- The majority of respondents (28.6%) obtain or seek information on food safety online. A little less than one quarter seek such information on product labels (23.7%) and in the media (23.5%).
- The largest share of respondents is concerned about additives, such as colour additives, preservatives or flavour intensifiers. Almost the same share is concerned about genetically modified food and the cloning of animals for food products. Compared to previous years, it can be noticed that the share of those who are concerned about food quality and freshness is constantly dropping; this share has dropped by 68.5% if compared to 2011 (84%). The concern regarding pesticide residue in fruit, vegetables and cereal has also somewhat decreased, including concern about the cloning of animals for food products.
- The greatest share of respondents (29.1%) think that animal products pose the greatest health risk, followed by sugar and sweet products (23.2%) and fats (13%). According to the respondents, other foodstuff groups present lower risks.
- The majority of respondents (71.5%) agree that food produced in the EU is safer than food imported from countries which are not Members of the European Economic Area. On the other hand, only 18.4% of respondents believe that we are eating safer food than we did in the past. This percentage is similar to the figure in 2015 (17.8%).
- Some 80.5% of respondents think that genetically modified food poses a risk to human health. A similar percentage believe that the cloning of animals for food products also poses such a risk.
- About one quarter sees potential in genetically modified food for developing new, better products, while the cloning of animals for food products and food consisting of nano-ingredients has less potential.
- According to the majority (over three quarters), genetically modified food and the cloning of animals for food products pose risks to human health.
- Some 15% of respondents are familiar with the European Food Safety Authority; 47.4% have heard of the Authority, but are not familiar with it, while 37.7% have never heard of it. The share of people familiar with the Authority is relatively stable.
- Most (50%) respondents in the survey on the dissemination of information on food safety trust scientists, who are followed by the European Food Safety Authority (41.6%) and consumer organisations (40.4%). The least credible source of disseminating information are the media (16.5%), according to the respondents. Nevertheless, the share of trust in various sources is rather stable. A trend of growing trust in state ministries and inspection services and a downward trend in trust in the media have been noticed.
- According to the respondents, the activities of non-governmental organisations (44.9%) contribute most to ensuring food safety. These are closely followed by acts of the European Union on food safety (43.4%) and the activities of the European Food Safety Authority (41.5%). Regarding the survey data from previous years, respondents attribute a somewhat greater contribution by the above institutions or organisations to the provision of food safety.

III. METHODOLOGICAL INTRODUCTION

The research is quantitative. CATI (computer-assisted telephone interviewing) was used to collect data. The telephone interviews were conducted by qualified interviewers.

A simple random sample was used; the sample size was n=700. The sample captured the entire population of Slovenia aged 18 and above. For representation purposes and the generalisation of the sample to the entire population, the sample was weighted in the analysis according to the latest data from the Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia (SURS) for the first semester 2017.

IV. REVIEW OF RESULTS

1.1. POPULATION STATISTICS

Some 700 respondents participated in the survey. The majority of respondents were aged between 35 and 54 (39.7%). The average sample age was 46.9 years. The majority of respondents (56.1%) have completed secondary school. One fourth of all respondents live in Central Slovenia, followed by residents from the Podravska (15.9%) and Savinjska regions (12.4%).

2.1. TRUST IN SAFE FOOD SUPPLIES

Almost half of respondents (49.5%) believe that the food they buy is safe. A trend in the increase of people who believe that the food they buy is safe has been noticed; compared to 2015, the share has increased by 10 percentage points (from 39.4%), and in comparison to 2013, the share increased by 25 percentage points (from 25.0%).

Do you trust safe food supplies, i.e. do you believe that the food you buy is safe?

Time comparison: percentage of assessments *I trust + I completely trust*.

Time comparison: mean average of assessments.

2.2. INFORMATION ON FOOD SAFETY

The majority of respondents (28.6%) obtain or seek information on food safety online, followed by product labels (23.7%) and the media (23.5%).

Where do you obtain or find information about food safety?

Open responses, categories of responses, comparable to 2015.

Where do you obtain or find information about food safety?

Open responses, 2017. Every item in the category *in the media, on the Internet, in books*, was placed in a new category.

2.3. CONCERN REGARDING FOOD SAFETY

The largest share of respondents (84.5%) is worried about additives, such as colour additives, preservatives or flavour intensifiers. To a somewhat lesser extent, respondents are worried about pesticide residues in fruit, vegetables and cereals (82.3%), veterinary drug residues in meat (81.7%), genetically modified food (81.0%) and the cloning of animals for food (80.1%). The respondents were least worried about allergic reactions to food/drinks; however, this percentage is also above 50%.

***In the continuation, we wish to know how concerned you are about food safety.
Please state for each of the following things whether it concerns you very much, quite or does not concern you.***

Percentage of assessments *quite concerned + very concerned*

*To ensure comparability of data with data from the preliminary research, the reply *I do not know* was marked in the analysis as a missing value.

2.3. CONCERN REGARDING FOOD SAFETY

2.3.1. FOOD QUALITY AND FRESHNESS

Are you very concerned, quite concerned or not concerned about the quality and freshness of food?

Some 21.8% of respondents are very concerned about food quality and freshness, and a further 46.7% are concerned. On the other hand, 31.4% are not concerned about the quality and freshness of food.

Time comparison: percentage of assessments *very concerned + quite concerned*.

The time comparison reveals that the share of people concerned about food quality and freshness is declining. In 2011, 84% of all respondents were concerned about food quality and freshness; in 2017, 68.5% of respondents were concerned.

*To ensure comparability of data with data from the preliminary research, the reply *I do not know* was marked in the analysis as a missing value.

2.3. CONCERN REGARDING FOOD SAFETY

2.3.2. FLAVOUR INTENSIFIERS

Are you very concerned, quite concerned or not concerned about additives, such as colour additives, preservatives or flavour intensifiers?

In the survey about flavour intensifiers, 46.4% of respondents are very concerned and 38.1% are quite concerned. Some 15.5% of respondents are not concerned about flavour intensifiers.

Time comparison: percentage of assessments *very concerned + quite concerned*.

Concern regarding flavour intensifiers is approximately at the same level as in 2015. The share of very and quite concerned respondents has not changed significantly over the years.

*To ensure comparability of data with data from the preliminary research, the reply *I do not know* was marked in the analysis as a missing value.

2.3. CONCERN REGARDING FOOD SAFETY

2.3.3. PESTICIDE RESIDUES IN FRUIT, VEGETABLES AND CEREALS

Are you very concerned, quite concerned or not concerned about pesticide residues in fruit, vegetables and cereals?

Fifty per cent of respondents are very concerned about pesticide residues in fruit, vegetables and cereals. Almost one third is quite concerned, while 17.7% of respondents are not concerned about pesticide residues in fruit, vegetables and cereals.

Time comparison: percentage of assessments *very concerned + quite concerned*.

Some 82.3% of respondents are concerned about pesticide residues in fruit, vegetables and cereals. Although the share has somewhat increased if compared to 2015, a downward trend in the share of concerned respondents can be noticed.

*To ensure comparability of data with data from the preliminary research, the reply *I do not know* was marked in the analysis as a missing value.

2.3. CONCERN REGARDING FOOD SAFETY

2.3.4. GENETICALLY MODIFIED FOOD

Are you very concerned, quite concerned or not concerned about genetically modified food?

Some 47.7% of respondents are very concerned about genetically modified food. One third is quite concerned, while 19% of respondents are not concerned about genetically modified food.

Time comparison: percentage of assessments *very concerned + quite concerned*.

Some 81% of respondents are concerned about genetically modified food. The percentage is comparable to that in 2015.

*To ensure comparability of data with data from the preliminary research, the reply *I do not know* was marked in the analysis as a missing value.

2.3. CONCERN REGARDING FOOD SAFETY

2.3.5. ANIMAL CLONING FOR FOOD PRODUCTS

Are you very concerned, quite concerned or not concerned about animal cloning for food?

Some 57.5% of respondents are very concerned about animal cloning for food products, and 22.6% are quite concerned about animal cloning. The cloning of animals for food is not a cause for concern for 19.9% of respondents.

Time comparison: percentage of assessments *very concerned + quite concerned*.

The time comparison chart shows that the share of people concerned about animal cloning for food products has been falling somewhat over the years; however, 80.1% of all respondents are still concerned about this matter.

*To ensure comparability of data with data from the preliminary research, the reply *I do not know* was marked in the analysis as a missing value.

2.3. CONCERN REGARDING FOOD SAFETY

2.3.6. NANO-INGREDIENTS IN FOOD

Are you very concerned, quite concerned or not concerned about nano-ingredients in food?

Some 29.9% of respondents are very concerned about nano-ingredients in food and a further 37.4% are concerned about nano-ingredients. A little less than one third is not concerned about nano-ingredients in food.

Time comparison: percentage of assessments *very concerned + quite concerned*.

The percentage of people concerned about nano-ingredients in food is somewhat lower than in previous years.

*To ensure comparability of data with data from the preliminary research, the reply *I do not know* was marked in the analysis as a missing value.

2.3. CONCERN REGARDING FOOD SAFETY

2.3.7. CONTAMINANTS IN FOODSTUFFS

Are you very concerned, quite concerned or not concerned about contaminants in foodstuffs, such as mercury in fish?

Contaminants in foodstuffs (mercury in fish) are of great concern for 43% of respondents. Some 34.3% of respondents are concerned about contaminants in foodstuffs, while 22.7% are not concerned.

Time comparison: percentage of assessments *very concerned + quite concerned*.

The share of people concerned about contaminants in foodstuffs is at the same level as in 2015.

*To ensure comparability of data with data from the preliminary research, the reply *I do not know* was marked in the analysis as a missing value.

2.3. CONCERN REGARDING FOOD SAFETY

2.3.8. VETERINARY DRUG RESIDUES IN MEAT

Are you very concerned, quite concerned or not concerned about veterinary drug residues (antibiotics, hormones) in meat?

Fifty per cent of respondents are very concerned about veterinary drug residues in meat and one third is quite concerned about them. Some 18.3% of respondents are not concerned about veterinary drug residues in meat.

Time comparison: percentage of assessments *very concerned + quite concerned*.

The share of people concerned about veterinary drug residues in meat decreased by merely one percentage point in comparison to 2015.

*To ensure comparability of data with data from the preliminary research, the reply *I do not know* was marked in the analysis as a missing value.

2.3. CONCERN REGARDING FOOD SAFETY

2.3.9. FOOD POISONING CAUSED BY THE PRESENCE OF BACTERIA

Are you very concerned, quite concerned or not concerned about food poisoning caused by the presence of bacteria (e.g. salmonella in eggs)?

One third of respondents is very concerned about bacteria-caused food poisoning (salmonella in eggs) and 29.9% are quite concerned about this matter. Food poisoning caused by the presence of bacteria is of no concern for 36.7% of respondents.

*To ensure comparability of data with data from the preliminary research, the reply *I do not know* was marked in the analysis as a missing value.

2.3. CONCERN REGARDING FOOD SAFETY

2.3.10. ALLERGIC REACTIONS TO FOOD/DRINKS

Are you very concerned, quite concerned or not concerned about allergic reactions to food/drinks?

Allergic reactions to food/drinks are of concern to 51.3% of respondents.

*To ensure comparability of data with data from the preliminary research, the reply *I do not know* was marked in the analysis as a missing value.

2.3. CONCERN REGARDING FOOD SAFETY

SUMMARY: time comparison

The time comparison chart reveals that concern about food quality and freshness decreased most over time, and concern about nano-ingredients in food has also somewhat decreased since the last survey (in 2015). In general, concern about food safety is at a similar level to 2015.

Please state for each of the following things whether it concerns you very much, quite or does not concern you.

Time comparison: percentage of assessments *quite concerned + very concerned*.

*To ensure comparability of data with data from the preliminary research, the reply *I do not know* was marked in the analysis as a missing value.

3.1. FOODSTUFFS POSING THE GREATEST HEALTH RISK

The greatest share of respondents (29.1%) think that animal products pose the greatest health risk, followed by sugar and sweet products (23.2%) and fats (13%). According to the respondents, other foodstuff groups present lower risks.

In your opinion, which foodstuffs that you consume pose the greatest health risk?

The main reason that these foodstuffs pose a health risk according to the respondents is that they cause diseases and ill-health. The respondents are also concerned about various additives, sugar content and the unknown origin of food.

Why do you think these foodstuffs pose a risk to your health?

*Open responses

4.1. FOOD SAFETY

We will read to you several statements regarding safe food supply. Please respond to each statement with I agree or I do not agree.

Do you agree or disagree with the statement: The food we consume now is safer than it was in the past.

Only 18.4% of respondents think that we eat safer food today than in the past, whereas 72.5% of respondents disagree.

Time comparison: percentage of assessments *I agree*.

Almost the same percentage of people as in 2015 think that the food we eat today is safer than it was in the past.

4.2. ADVANTAGES OF USING NEW TECHNOLOGIES

Do you agree or disagree with the statement: In the field of food, the advantages

of using new technologies and globalisation are greater than the risks.

Some 40.7% of respondents agree that the advantages of using new technologies in the field of food are greater than the risks.

Time comparison: percentage of assessments *I agree*.

Compared to 2015, the share of those agreeing that the advantages of using new technologies in the field of food are greater than the risks increased by somewhat more than four percentage points.

4.3. PRODUCT LABELS

Do you agree or disagree with the statement: The label on a product provides me with all the necessary information on the foodstuff.

Some 43.4% of respondents disagree with the statement that product labels provide all information necessary about a foodstuff, while 35.9% of respondents agree with the statement.

Time comparison: percentage of assessments *I agree*.

Compared to 2015, the share of those agreeing with the statement that product labels provide all information necessary about foodstuffs increased by more than eight percentage points.

4.4. MADE IN THE EU

Do you agree or disagree with the statement: Food produced in the EU is safer than food imported from third countries (i.e. countries which are not Member States of the European Economic Area).

The majority of respondents (71.5%) agree that food produced in the EU is safer than food imported from countries which are not Members of the European Economic Area.

4.5. SUMMARY: TIME COMPARISON

Compared to 2015, a somewhat larger share of respondents agree with the statement that *the product label is the source of all necessary information about a foodstuff* and the statement that *the advantages of using new technologies and globalisation in the field of food are greater than the risks*. Almost the same share of respondents in both years agreed with the statement that *the food we consume today is safer than it was in the past*.

We will read to you several statements regarding safe food supply. Please respond to each statement with *I agree* or *I do not agree*.

Time comparison: percentage of assessments *I agree*.

5.1. GENETICALLY MODIFIED FOOD 5.1.1. POSSIBILITY OF DEVELOPING NEW, BETTER FOOD PRODUCTS

We will read a few statements now and we ask you to say whether you think the statements are true or false.

Genetically modified food offers the possibility of developing new, better food products.

Only a small share of respondents (26.7%) think that genetically modified food offers the possibility of developing new, better food products. Some 61.8% of respondents disagree with the above statement.

Time comparison: percentage of assessments *Yes, it is true.*

The percentage of those who see the possibility of developing new, better food products from genetically modified food is almost identical to the percentage in 2015.

Genetically modified food poses a risk to human health.

Some 80.5% of respondents think that genetically modified food poses a risk to human health.

Time comparison: percentage of assessments *Yes, it is true.*

A time comparison shows that the share of respondents who think that genetically modified food presents a risk to human health increased slightly in comparison to the past year, but is still lower than in the 2013 survey.

Genetically modified food is ethically acceptable.

Genetically modified food is ethically acceptable only to a small share of respondents (21.4%). Some 70.5% of respondents are of the opinion that genetically modified food is not ethically acceptable.

Time comparison: percentage of assessments *Yes, it is true.*

The share of those who think that genetically modified food is ethically acceptable was one percentage point lower than in 2015.

5.2. FOOD CONTAINING NANO-INGREDIENTS 5.2.1. POSSIBILITY OF DEVELOPING NEW, BETTER FOOD PRODUCTS

Food containing nano-ingredients presents the possibility of developing new, better food products.

Some 14.2% of respondents believe that food containing nano-ingredients presents the possibility of developing new, better food products. One third disagrees with this statement, while as many as 52% of respondents have no opinion on the matter.

Time comparison: percentage of assessments *Yes, it is true.*

The share of people who see the potential to develop new, better food products from food containing nano-ingredients decreased by a half in comparison to 2015.

5.2. FOOD CONTAINING NANO-INGREDIENTS 5.2.2. RISK TO HUMAN HEALTH

Food containing nano-ingredients poses a risk to human health.

Some 42.7% of respondents think that food containing nano-ingredients poses a risk to human health. Some 9.6% of respondents disagree, and 47.7% have no opinion on the matter.

Time comparison: percentage of assessments *Yes, it is true.*

A time comparison with 2015 reveals that the share of respondents who believe that food containing nano-ingredients poses risk to human health decreased by twenty percentage points.

5.2. FOOD CONTAINING NANO-INGREDIENTS 5.2.3. ETHICAL ACCEPTABILITY

Food containing nano-ingredients is ethically acceptable.

Food containing nano-ingredients is ethically acceptable for 11.8% of respondents. Some 39.1% of respondents are of the opinion that it is not ethically acceptable, and 49.1% have no opinion on this matter.

Time comparison: percentage of assessments Yes, it is true.

The share of those who think that food containing nano-ingredients is ethically acceptable decreased by ten percentage points in comparison to 2015.

5.3. ANIMAL CLONING FOR FOOD PRODUCTS

5.3.1. POSSIBILITY OF DEVELOPING NEW, BETTER FOOD PRODUCTS

Animal cloning for food products presents the possibility of developing new, better food products.

Some 16.1% of respondents are of the opinion that animal cloning for food products presents the possibility of developing new, better food products. Some 72.8% of respondents disagree with the above statement.

Time comparison: percentage of assessments *Yes, it is true.*

The percentage of those who see the possibility of developing new, better food products in animal cloning has been quite stable over time.

Animal cloning for food products poses a risk to human health.

As many as 78.4% of respondents are certain that animal cloning for food products poses a risk to human health.

Time comparison: percentage of assessments *Yes, it is true.*

A time comparison reveals that the share of respondents who think that animal cloning for food products poses a risk to human health has barely changed over the years.

Animal cloning for food products is ethically acceptable.

Animal cloning for food products is ethically acceptable for 11.9% of respondents. Some 82.1% of respondents disagree with the above statement.

Time comparison: percentage of assessments *Yes, it is true.*

A time comparison reveals that the share of respondents who think that animal cloning for food products is ethically acceptable has barely changed over the years.

5. GENETICALLY MODIFIED FOOD, FOOD CONTAINING NANO-INGREDIENTS, CLONING OF ANIMALS FOR FOOD PRODUCTS

SUMMARY: TIME COMPARISON

Time comparisons show that the opinion of people regarding issues linked to genetically modified food and animal cloning for food products has not changed significantly over the years. Changes are evident only in the opinion relating to food containing nano-ingredients.

* Percentage of responses Yes, it is true.

5. GENETICALLY MODIFIED FOOD, FOOD CONTAINING NANO-INGREDIENTS, CLONING OF ANIMALS FOR FOOD PRODUCTS

SUMMARY: TIME COMPARISON

According to the respondents, neither the foodstuff group nor activity (genetically modified food; food containing nano-ingredients, animal cloning) offers many possibilities for developing new, better food products. Nevertheless, the respondents ascribe the most potential to genetically modified food (26.7%). Furthermore, the majority of respondents believe that the relevant foodstuff groups or activities are not ethically acceptable. Only a minority thinks they are acceptable, mostly in the case of genetically modified food (21.4%). According to the majority (over three quarters), genetically modified food and the cloning of animals for food products pose risks to human health.

Presents the possibility of developing new, better food products

Poses risk to human health

Ethical unacceptability

* Percentage of responses Yes, it is true.

6.1. KNOWLEDGE OF THE EUROPEAN FOOD SAFETY AUTHORITY

Are you familiar with, or have you heard of, the European Food Safety Authority, which was established in 2002?

Some 15% of respondents are familiar with the European Food Safety Authority; 47.4% have heard of the Authority, but are not familiar with it, while 37.7% have never heard of it.

Time comparison: percentage of assessments *Yes, I am familiar with it.*

The percentage of people familiar with the European Food Safety Authority has been approximately the same over the years.

7.1. TRUSTING SOURCES OF INFORMATION ON FOOD SAFETY

We will read to you various sources. Please assess the level of TRUST you have in each source for disseminating information about food safety and possible risks. Use the scale from 1 to 5, where 1 means that you do not trust the source of information on food safety and 5 means that you completely trust the source. You are also free to give scores from 2 to 4.

To what extent do you trust information from ... about food safety and possible risks?

According to the respondents, the most credible source of information on food safety are scientists, since one half of the participants in the survey trust them. They are followed by the European Food Safety Authority and consumer organisations. The least credible sources, which only 16.5% of respondents trust, are the media and the food industry which enjoys the trust of 18.2% of respondents.

The same categorisation is obtained from calculating the mean average.

Comparison: mean average.

7.1. TRUSTING SOURCES OF INFORMATION ON FOOD SAFETY 7.1.1. CONSUMER ORGANISATIONS

To what extent do you trust consumer organisations' information about food safety and possible risks?

Some 40.4% of respondents trust consumer organisations' information about food safety and possible risks; 22.7% of respondents expressed their distrust.

Time comparison: mean average.

In comparison to past research, respondents' trust in consumer organisations has slightly increased.

7.1. TRUSTING SOURCES OF INFORMATION ON FOOD SAFETY

7.1.2. SCIENTISTS

To what extent do you trust scientists' information about food safety and possible risks?

Some 50% of respondents trust scientists' information about food safety and possible risks, while 15.3% of respondents expressed distrust.

Time comparison: mean average.

In comparison to the 2015 research, respondents' trust in scientists has somewhat increased and is at the same level as in 2013.

7.1. TRUSTING SOURCES OF INFORMATION ON FOOD SAFETY

7.1.3. EUROPEAN FOOD SAFETY AUTHORITY

To what extent do you trust the European Food Safety Authority's information about food safety and possible risks?

Some 41.6% of respondents trust the European Food Safety Authority's information about food safety and possible risks, while 20% of respondents expressed distrust.

Time comparison: mean average.

In comparison to past research, respondents' trust in the European Food Safety Authority has somewhat increased.

7.1. TRUSTING SOURCES OF INFORMATION ON FOOD SAFETY

To what extent do you trust state ministries' and inspection services' information about food safety and possible risks?

7.1.4. STATE MINISTRIES AND INSPECTION SERVICES

Some 31.8% of respondents trust state ministries' and inspection services' information about food safety and possible risks, while 33.7% of respondents expressed distrust.

Time comparison: mean average.

A trend of growing trust in state ministries and inspection services has been noticed over the years.

7.1. TRUSTING SOURCES OF INFORMATION ON FOOD SAFETY

7.1.5. MEDIA

To what extent do you trust information from the media about food safety and possible risks?

Some 16.5% of respondents trust information from the media about food safety and possible risks, while 45.3% of respondents expressed distrust.

Time comparison: mean average.

A downward trend of respondents' trust in the media has been noticed over the years.

7.1. TRUSTING SOURCES OF INFORMATION ON FOOD SAFETY

7.1.6. FOOD INDUSTRY

To what extent do you trust the food industry's information about food safety and possible risks?

Some 18.2% of respondents trust the food industry's information about food safety and possible risks, while 43.5% of respondents expressed distrust.

Time comparison: mean average.

Compared to the 2015 research, respondents' trust in the food industry remained at the same level.

7.1. TRUSTING SOURCES OF INFORMATION ON FOOD SAFETY

7.1.7. SUMMARY: TIME COMPARISON

The time comparison reveals that respondents' trust in scientists, the European Food Safety Authority, consumer organisations, state ministries and inspection services concerning the reliability of their information on food safety and possible risks has been growing. Trust in the food industry's information has been rather stable over the years, while trust in the media has been somewhat decreasing.

To what extent do you trust information from ... about food safety and possible risks?

Time comparison: mean average.

8.1. CONTRIBUTING TO THE PROVISION OF FOOD SAFETY

We will name various institutions or organisations and we ask you to assess how much you think they contribute with their work to providing food safety. Use the scale from 1 to 5, where 1 means that they do not contribute at all and 5 means that they contribute a lot to providing food safety.

To what extent does ... contribute with its work to providing food safety?

According to the respondents, the activities of NGOs, the acts of the European Union on food safety and activities of the European Food Safety Authority contribute equally to providing food safety. Over 40% of respondents believe that they contribute or contribute greatly. At the same time, almost the same share of respondents has no particular opinion on this issue (they neither contribute nor not contribute). According to the opinion of participants in the research, the work of Slovenian ministries and inspection services contributes least to providing food safety.

Comparison: mean average.

The same categorisation is obtained from calculating the mean average.

8.1. CONTRIBUTING TO THE PROVISION OF FOOD SAFETY

8.1.1. EUROPEAN FOOD SAFETY AUTHORITY

To what extent do the activities of the European Food Safety Authority contribute to providing food safety?

Some 41.5% of respondents think that the activities of the European Food Safety Authority contribute to providing food safety. On the other hand, 14.4% think that it does not contribute to providing food safety.

Time comparison: mean average.

Compared to the results from previous years, more respondents think that the activities of the European Food Safety Authority contribute to providing food safety.

8.1. CONTRIBUTING TO THE PROVISION OF FOOD SAFETY

8.1.2. ACTS OF THE EUROPEAN UNION ON FOOD SAFETY

To what extent do the acts of the European Union on food safety contribute to providing food safety?

Some 43.4% of respondents are of the opinion that the acts of the European Union on food safety contribute to providing food safety. On the other hand, 16.6% think that they do not contribute to providing food safety.

Time comparison: mean average.

Compared to the results from previous years, more respondents think that the acts of the European Union contribute to providing food safety.

8.1. CONTRIBUTING TO THE PROVISION OF FOOD SAFETY

To what extent does the work of Slovenian ministries and inspection services contribute to providing food safety?

Time comparison: mean average.

8.1.3. WORK OF SLOVENIAN MINISTRIES AND INSPECTION SERVICES

Some 31.6% of respondents is of the opinion that work of Slovenian ministries and inspection services contributes to providing food safety. On the other hand, 30.8 % think that it does not contribute to providing food safety.

Compared to the results from previous years, more respondents think that the work of Slovenian ministries and inspection services contributes to providing food safety.

8.1. CONTRIBUTING TO THE PROVISION OF FOOD SAFETY

To what extent do the activities of non-governmental organisations contribute to providing food safety?

Time comparison: mean average.

8.1.4. ACTIVITIES OF NON-GOVERNMENTAL ORGANISATIONS

Some 44.9% of respondents think that the activities of non-governmental organisations contribute to providing food safety. On the other hand, 16.3% think that they do not contribute to providing food safety.

The average assessment regarding the contribution of NGOs to providing food safety has been stable over the years.

8.1. CONTRIBUTING TO THE PROVISION OF FOOD SAFETY

8.1.5. SUMMARY: TIME COMPARISON

The time comparison reveals a growing trend in the contribution to the provision of food safety ascribed to institutions or organisations (activities of NGOs; acts of the European Union on food safety; activities of the European Food Safety Authority; work of Slovenian ministries and inspection services). Over the years, respondents assessed that Slovenian ministries and inspection services contribute least to providing food safety.

To what extent does ... contribute with its work to providing food safety?

Time comparison: mean average.

V. ATTACHMENTS

V. ATTACHMENTS

The table below displays results by socio-demographic categories.

Display: Percentage by socio-demographic categories; mean average by socio-demographic categories

	Do you trust safe food supplies, i.e. do you believe that the food you buy is safe?					Hi-signif.*	Mean average	Hi-signif.**
	I do not trust at all	I do not trust	Neither nor	I trust	I trust completely			
Gender						,90		,63
men	5,9	17,5	28	42,4	6,2		3,25	
women	4,9	17,6	26,9	45,1	5,5		3,29	
Education						,00		,01
Primary or less	3,6	28,3	31,2	35,5	1,4		3,02	
Vocational/secondary	6,6	12,7	27,5	46,1	7,1		3,34	
Post-secondary, higher or more	4,1	20,1	24,9	44,4	6,5		3,3	
Age						,04		,00
18-34 years	4,9	12,4	24,9	49,7	8,1		3,43	
35-54 years	5,4	16,2	27,4	44,4	6,5		3,3	
55 years and more	5,9	23,2	29,5	38	3,4		3,1	
Region						,53		,63
Pomurska region	0	30	32,5	35	2,5		3,12	
Podravska region	7,1	22,3	19,6	44,6	6,3		3,22	
Koroška region	0	20	36	36	8		3,31	
Savinjska region	6,9	11,5	28,7	48,3	4,6		3,32	
Zasavska region	0	21,1	21,1	52,6	5,3		3,37	
Spodnjeposavska region	3,7	18,5	37	33,3	7,4		3,2	
South-eastern Slovenia	6,4	17	25,5	46,8	4,3		3,25	
Central Slovenia	3,9	14,4	29,3	43,6	8,8		3,4	
Gorenjska region	10,4	13,4	25,4	47,8	3		3,2	
Notranjsko-kraška region	11,1	0	44,4	44,4	0		3,27	
Goriška region	5	22,5	25	40	7,5		3,27	
Obalno-kraška region	7,9	26,3	26,3	39,5	0		2,96	
Total	5,4	17,6	27,5	43,7	5,8		3,27	

NOTE: differences are marked with various colours; green – data are statistically significantly higher regarding the entire population; grey – data are statistically significantly lower regarding the entire population

* Differences between groups are calculated according to the χ^2 method.

** Differences between groups are calculated according to the ANOVA method.

V. ATTACHMENTS

The table below displays results by socio-demographic categories.

Display: Percentage by socio-demographic categories

Are you very concerned, quite concerned or not concerned about the quality and freshness of food?				
	I am very concerned	I am quite concerned	I am not concerned	Hi-signif. *
Gender				,67
men	21,3	45,7	33	
women	22,4	47,7	29,9	
Education				,36
Primary or less	17,5	53,3	29,2	
Vocational/secondary	23,7	45,4	30,9	
Post-secondary, higher or more	20,8	44,6	34,5	
Age				,17
18-34 years	26,6	39,1	34,2	
35-54 years	20,5	49,3	30,2	
55 years and more	20	49,8	30,2	
Region				,68
Pomurska region	25	42,5	32,5	
Podravska region	23,4	41,4	35,1	
Koroška region	8,3	66,7	25	
Savinjska region	27,3	43,2	29,5	
Zasavska region	31,6	31,6	36,8	
Spodnjeposavska region	19,2	34,6	46,2	
South-eastern Slovenia	25	43,8	31,3	
Central Slovenia	17,7	50,8	31,5	
Gorenjska region	23,5	44,1	32,4	
Notranjsko-kraška region	16,7	55,6	27,8	
Goriška region	23,7	50	26,3	
Obalno-kraška region	21,1	57,9	21,1	
Total	21,8	46,7	31,4	

NOTE: differences are marked with various colours; green – data are statistically significantly higher regarding the entire population; grey – data are statistically significantly lower regarding the entire population

* Differences between groups are calculated according to the χ^2 method.

V. ATTACHMENTS

The table below displays results by socio-demographic categories.

Display: Percentage by socio-demographic categories

Are you very concerned, quite concerned or not concerned about additives, such as colour additives, preservatives or flavour intensifiers?				
	I am very concerned	I am quite concerned	I am not concerned	Hi-signif.*
Gender ,09				
men	43,6	38	18,4	
women	49,3	38,2	12,5	
Education ,30				
Primary or less	45,7	36,2	18,1	
Vocational/secondary	46,4	36,7	16,8	
Post-secondary, higher or more	46,4	42,9	10,7	
Age ,00				
18-34 years	35,1	41,6	23,2	
35-54 years	48,6	40,6	10,8	
55 years and more	52,8	31,9	15,3	
Region ,32				
Pomurska region	62,5	30	7,5	
Podravska region	51,4	32,4	16,2	
Koroška region	56	36	8	
Savinjska region	42,5	40,2	17,2	
Zasavska region	50	35	15	
Spodnjeposavska region	23,1	61,5	15,4	
South-eastern Slovenia	51,1	40,4	8,5	
Central Slovenia	40,6	42,8	16,7	
Gorenjska region	52,2	28,4	19,4	
Notranjsko-kraška region	44,4	38,9	16,7	
Goriška region	42,1	36,8	21,1	
Obalno-kraška region	47,4	39,5	13,2	
Total	46,4	38,1	15,6	

NOTE: differences are marked with various colours; green – data are statistically significantly higher regarding the entire population; grey – data are statistically significantly lower regarding the entire population

* Differences between groups are calculated according to the χ^2 method.

V. ATTACHMENTS

The table below displays results by socio-demographic categories.

Display: Percentage by socio-demographic categories

Are you very concerned, quite concerned or not concerned about pesticide residues in fruit, vegetables and cereals?

	I am very concerned	I am quite concerned	I am not concerned	Hi-signif.*
Gender				,29
men	47,7	32,8	19,5	
women	53,4	30,9	15,7	
Education				,00
Primary or less	43,4	27,9	28,7	
Vocational/secondary	51,5	31,6	16,8	
Post-secondary, higher or more	53,8	35,5	10,7	
Age				,00
18-34 years	39,1	37,5	23,4	
35-54 years	53,6	32,7	13,7	
55 years and more	55,6	26,5	17,9	
Region				,69
Pomurska region	50	32,5	17,5	
Podravska region	54,1	27	18,9	
Koroška region	62,5	20,8	16,7	
Savinjska region	49,4	35,6	14,9	
Zasavska region	57,1	23,8	19	
Spodnjeposavska region	34,6	50	15,4	
South-eastern Slovenia	56,3	27,1	16,7	
Central Slovenia	48	31,3	20,7	
Gorenjska region	49,3	32,8	17,9	
Notranjsko-kraška region	50	33,3	16,7	
Goriška region	52,6	26,3	21,1	
Obalno-kraška region	48,7	48,7	2,6	
Total	50,5	31,8	17,7	

NOTE: differences are marked with various colours; green – data are statistically significantly higher regarding the entire population; grey – data are statistically significantly lower regarding the entire population

* Differences between groups are calculated according to the χ^2 method.

V. ATTACHMENTS

The table below displays results by socio-demographic categories.

Display: Percentage by socio-demographic categories

Are you very concerned, quite concerned or not concerned about genetically modified food?				
	I am very concerned	I am quite concerned	I am not concerned	Hi-signif.*
Gender				
				,57
men	45,6	34,9	19,5	
women	49,7	31,7	18,6	
Education				
				,76
Primary or less	48,8	30,9	20,3	
Vocational/secondary	49,1	33,1	17,8	
Post-secondary, higher or more	44	35,5	20,5	
Age				
				,00
18-34 years	30,2	40,1	29,7	
35-54 years	51,6	32,6	15,8	
55 years and more	57,1	28,6	14,3	
Region				
				,11
Pomurska region	54,1	32,4	13,5	
Podravska region	56	25,7	18,3	
Koroška region	34,8	39,1	26,1	
Savinjska region	54,8	26,2	19	
Zasavska region	38,9	38,9	22,2	
Spodnjeposavska region	24	48	28	
South-eastern Slovenia	59,1	25	15,9	
Central Slovenia	42,9	39	18,1	
Gorenjska region	49,2	32,3	18,5	
Notranjsko-kraška region	52,9	23,5	23,5	
Goriška region	47,2	27,8	25	
Obalno-kraška region	33,3	55,6	11,1	
Total	47,7	33,3	19	

NOTE: differences are marked with various colours; green – data are statistically significantly higher regarding the entire population; grey – data are statistically significantly lower regarding the entire population

* Differences between groups are calculated according to the χ^2 method.

V. ATTACHMENTS

The table below displays results by socio-demographic categories.

Display: Percentage by socio-demographic categories

Are you very concerned, quite concerned or not concerned about animal cloning for food?				
	I am very concerned	I am quite concerned	I am not concerned	Hi-signif.*
Gender				
				,02
men	54,1	21,8	24,1	
women	61	23,5	15,5	
Education				
				,45
Primary or less	60,8	21,7	17,5	
Vocational/secondary	58,6	23	18,5	
Post-secondary, higher or more	52,8	22,7	24,5	
Age				
				,00
18-34 years	41	24,2	34,8	
35-54 years	62	21,4	16,5	
55 years and more	65,3	22,8	11,9	
Region				
				,45
Pomurska region	57,9	31,6	10,5	
Podravska region	64,4	16,3	19,2	
Koroška region	45,8	33,3	20,8	
Savinjska region	62,7	21,7	15,7	
Zasavska region	70,6	17,6	11,8	
Spodnjeposavska region	58,3	20,8	20,8	
South-eastern Slovenia	67,4	18,6	14	
Central Slovenia	52	22,2	25,7	
Gorenjska region	62,1	16,7	21,2	
Notranjsko-kraška region	47,1	41,2	11,8	
Goriška region	45,9	29,7	24,3	
Obalno-kraška region	50	28,9	21,1	
Total	57,5	22,6	19,9	

NOTE: differences are marked with various colours; green – data are statistically significantly higher regarding the entire population; grey – data are statistically significantly lower regarding the entire population

* Differences between groups are calculated according to the χ^2 method.

V. ATTACHMENTS

The table below displays results by socio-demographic categories.

Display: Percentage by socio-demographic categories

Are you very concerned, quite concerned or not concerned about nano-ingredients in food?				
	I am very concerned	I am quite concerned	I am not concerned	Hi-signif.*
Gender				
men	25,9	38,5	35,6	,09
women	35	36	28,9	
Education				
Primary or less	32,3	38,7	29	,86
Vocational/secondary	31,1	36,3	32,6	
Post-secondary, higher or more	26,1	40	33,9	
Age				
18-34 years	23,1	32,7	44,2	,00
35-54 years	30,6	39,3	30,1	
55 years and more	37,7	40,4	21,9	
Region				
Pomurska region	25,9	44,4	29,6	,80
Podravska region	33,8	31,2	35,1	
Koroška region	28,6	57,1	14,3	
Savinjska region	30,6	35,5	33,9	
Zasavska region	25	41,7	33,3	
Spodnjeposavska region	13,6	36,4	50	
South-eastern Slovenia	30,4	39,1	30,4	
Central Slovenia	28,4	35,8	35,8	
Gorenjska region	39	34,1	26,8	
Notranjsko-kraška region	28,6	35,7	35,7	
Goriška region	40	35	25	
Obalno-kraška region	20	56	24	
Total	29,9	37,4	32,6	

NOTE: differences are marked with various colours; green – data are statistically significantly higher regarding the entire population; grey – data are statistically significantly lower regarding the entire population

* Differences between groups are calculated according to the χ^2 method.

V. ATTACHMENTS

The table below displays results by socio-demographic categories.

Display: Percentage by socio-demographic categories

Are you very concerned, quite concerned or not concerned about contaminants in foodstuffs, such as mercury in fish, for example?				
	I am very concerned	I am quite concerned	I am not concerned	Hi-signif.*
Gender				,22
men	41,4	33,3	25,3	
women	44,9	35,3	19,8	
Education				,35
Primary or less	44,4	28,6	27,1	
Vocational/secondary	41,3	36,3	22,4	
Post-secondary, higher or more	45,8	34,5	19,6	
Age				,00
18-34 years	30,2	41,9	27,9	
35-54 years	46,7	32,6	20,7	
55 years and more	48,5	30,4	21,1	
Region				,43
Pomurska region	40	35	25	
Podravska region	49,1	35,5	15,5	
Koroška region	30,4	52,2	17,4	
Savinjska region	42,7	35,4	22	
Zasavska region	63,2	15,8	21,1	
Spodnjeposavska region	50	30,8	19,2	
South-eastern Slovenia	41,3	23,9	34,8	
Central Slovenia	38,4	39	22,6	
Gorenjska region	42,4	30,3	27,3	
Notranjsko-kraška region	35,3	41,2	23,5	
Goriška region	50	21,1	28,9	
Obalno-kraška region	43,6	35,9	20,5	
Total	43	34,3	22,7	

NOTE: differences are marked with various colours; green – data are statistically significantly higher regarding the entire population; grey – data are statistically significantly lower regarding the entire population

* Differences between groups are calculated according to the χ^2 method.

V. ATTACHMENTS

The table below displays results by socio-demographic categories.

Display: Percentage by socio-demographic categories

Are you very concerned, quite concerned or not concerned about veterinary drug residues (antibiotics, hormones) in meat?

	I am very concerned	I am quite concerned	I am not concerned	Hi-signif.*
Gender				,82
men	49,1	32,8	18	
women	50,9	30,5	18,6	
Education				,01
Primary or less	43,5	27,5	29	
Vocational/secondary	51,3	31,8	16,9	
Post-secondary, higher or more	52,4	34,5	13,1	
Age				,00
18-34 years	37,3	37,9	24,9	
35-54 years	51,3	33,6	15,2	
55 years and more	58,3	24,6	17,1	
Region				,40
Pomurska region	57,5	32,5	10	
Podravska region	48,2	26,4	25,5	
Koroška region	52,4	33,3	14,3	
Savinjska region	52,4	32,1	15,5	
Zasavska region	55	25	20	
Spodnje-posavska region	30,8	53,8	15,4	
South-eastern Slovenia	60,9	23,9	15,2	
Central Slovenia	48	32,4	19,6	
Gorenjska region	54,7	26,6	18,8	
Notranjsko-kraška region	47,1	35,3	17,6	
Goriška region	52,6	26,3	21,1	
Obalno-kraška region	37,8	51,4	10,8	
Total	50	31,7	18,3	

NOTE: differences are marked with various colours; green – data are statistically significantly higher regarding the entire population; grey – data are statistically significantly lower regarding the entire population

* Differences between groups are calculated according to the χ^2 method.

V. ATTACHMENTS

The table below displays results by socio-demographic categories.

Display: Percentage by socio-demographic categories

Are you very concerned, quite concerned or not concerned about food poisoning caused by the presence of bacteria (e.g. salmonella in eggs)?				
	I am very concerned	I am quite concerned	I am not concerned	Hi-signif.*
Gender				,20
men	31	29,3	39,8	
women	36	30,5	33,4	
Education				,26
Primary or less	37,5	23,5	39	
Vocational/secondary	34,3	30,4	35,3	
Post-secondary, higher or more	28,4	33,7	37,9	
Age				,20
18-34 years	27,6	36,2	36,2	
35-54 years	34,9	28,1	37,1	
55 years and more	36,2	27,2	36,6	
Region				,12
Pomurska region	40	25	35	
Podravska region	42,3	25,2	32,4	
Koroška region	20,8	54,2	25	
Savinjska region	41,4	26,4	32,2	
Zasavska region	25	20	55	
Spodnjeposavska region	28	36	36	
South-eastern Slovenia	35,4	22,9	41,7	
Central Slovenia	27,1	32,6	40,3	
Gorenjska region	33,8	23,5	42,6	
Notranjsko-kraška region	22,2	38,9	38,9	
Goriška region	29,7	40,5	29,7	
Obalno-kraška region	31,6	36,8	31,6	
Total	33,4	29,9	36,7	

NOTE: differences are marked with various colours; green – data are statistically significantly higher regarding the entire population; grey – data are statistically significantly lower regarding the entire population

* Differences between groups are calculated according to the χ^2 method.

V. ATTACHMENTS

The table below displays results by socio-demographic categories.

Display: Percentage by socio-demographic categories

Are you very concerned, quite concerned or not concerned about allergic reactions to food/drinks?				
	I am very concerned	I am quite concerned	I am not concerned	Hi-signif.*
Gender				
men	17,5	31,8	50,7	,04
women	25,4	28,1	46,6	
Education				
Primary or less	20,9	28,7	50,4	,97
Vocational/secondary	21,8	29,4	48,8	
Post-secondary, higher or more	20,7	32	47,3	
Age				
18-34 years	13,7	25,8	60,4	,00
35-54 years	24,4	32	43,6	
55 years and more	23,8	30,8	45,4	
Region				
Pomurska region	24,4	24,4	51,2	,69
Podravska region	26,4	31,8	41,8	
Koroška region	20	36	44	
Savinjska region	22,1	32,6	45,3	
Zasavska region	10,5	26,3	63,2	
Spodnjeposavska region	18,5	48,1	33,3	
South-eastern Slovenia	18,8	35,4	45,8	
Central Slovenia	19,8	28,5	51,7	
Gorenjska region	25	23,4	51,6	
Notranjsko-kraška region	23,5	23,5	52,9	
Goriška region	26,3	31,6	42,1	
Obalno-kraška region	12,8	23,1	64,1	
Total	21,3	30	48,7	

NOTE: differences are marked with various colours; green – data are statistically significantly higher regarding the entire population; grey – data are statistically significantly lower regarding the entire population

* Differences between groups are calculated according to the χ^2 method.

V. ATTACHMENTS

The table below displays results by socio-demographic categories.

Display: Percentage by socio-demographic categories

The food we consume now is safer than it was in the past.				
	I do not agree	I agree	Neither nor	Hi-signif.*
Gender				,73
men	73,3	19	7,7	
women	72,7	18	9,3	
Education				,42
Primary or less	66,7	23,2	10,1	
Vocational/secondary	75,3	16,7	8	
Post-secondary, higher or more	73,2	19	7,7	
Age				,09
18-34 years	69,4	18,6	12	
35-54 years	75,5	19,5	5,1	
55 years and more	72,8	17,4	9,8	
Region				,18
Pomurska region	72,5	17,5	10	
Podravska region	72,5	23,9	3,7	
Koroška region	79,2	20,8	0	
Savinjska region	70,1	20,7	9,2	
Zasavska region	75	15	10	
Spodnjeposavska region	61,5	15,4	23,1	
South-eastern Slovenia	65,3	18,4	16,3	
Central Slovenia	77,3	15,3	7,4	
Gorenjska region	80,9	14,7	4,4	
Notranjsko-kraška region	72,2	11,1	16,7	
Goriška region	61,5	23,1	15,4	
Obalno-kraška region	74,4	20,5	5,1	
Total	73,1	18,5	8,4	

NOTE: differences are marked with various colours; green – data are statistically significantly higher regarding the entire population; grey – data are statistically significantly lower regarding the entire population

* Differences between groups are calculated according to the χ^2 method.

V. ATTACHMENTS

The table below displays results by socio-demographic categories.

Display: Percentage by socio-demographic categories

In the field of food, the advantages of using new technologies and globalisation are greater than the risks.				
	I do not agree	I agree	Neither nor	Hi-signif.*
Gender				
men	39	46,6	14,3	
women	31,8	43,3	24,9	
Education				
Primary or less	34,1	35,8	30,1	
Vocational/secondary	33,2	50,1	16,6	
Post-secondary, higher or more	41,9	40,6	17,4	
Age				
18-34 years	31	48,8	20,2	
35-54 years	35,8	47,5	16,7	
55 years and more	38,9	38,9	22,1	
Region				
Pomurska region	35,9	33,3	30,8	
Podravska region	39	50,5	10,5	
Koroška region	34,8	56,5	8,7	
Savinjska region	26,3	56,6	17,1	
Zasavska region	25	37,5	37,5	
Spodnje-posavska region	39,1	30,4	30,4	
South-eastern Slovenia	30	50	20	
Central Slovenia	39,3	43,5	17,3	
Gorenjska region	41	36,1	23	
Notranjsko-kraška region	25	43,8	31,3	
Goriška region	35,3	35,3	29,4	
Obalno-kraška region	29,4	52,9	17,6	
Total	35,5	45	19,5	

NOTE: differences are marked with various colours; green – data are statistically significantly higher regarding the entire population; grey – data are statistically significantly lower regarding the entire population

* Differences between groups are calculated according to the χ^2 method.

V. ATTACHMENTS

The table below displays results by socio-demographic categories.

Display: Percentage by socio-demographic categories

A product label is the source of all the information I need about a foodstuff.		I do not agree	I agree	Neither nor	Hi-signif.*
Gender					,28
men		44,4	38,1	17,5	
women		43,3	34,6	22,1	
Education					,00
Primary or less		32,6	36,3	31,1	
Vocational/secondary		45,2	36,2	18,5	
Post-secondary, higher or more		50,3	36,1	13,6	
Age					,01
18-34 years		53,8	30,4	15,8	
35-54 years		43,6	36,4	20	
55 years and more		36,3	41	22,6	
Region					,37
Pomurska region		36,8	34,2	28,9	
Podravska region		50,9	38,2	10,9	
Koroška region		36	40	24	
Savinjska region		37,2	48,8	14	
Zasavska region		36,8	36,8	26,3	
Spodnjeposavska region		34,6	50	15,4	
South-eastern Slovenia		45,8	35,4	18,8	
Central Slovenia		46,7	30,6	22,8	
Gorenjska region		41,8	35,8	22,4	
Notranjsko-kraška region		41,2	41,2	17,6	
Goriška region		47,4	26,3	26,3	
Obalno-kraška region		46,2	33,3	20,5	
Total		43,9	36,3	19,7	

NOTE: differences are marked with various colours; green – data are statistically significantly higher regarding the entire population; grey – data are statistically significantly lower regarding the entire population

* Differences between groups are calculated according to the χ^2 method.

V. ATTACHMENTS

The table below displays results by socio-demographic categories.

Display: Percentage by socio-demographic categories

Food produced in the EU is safer than food imported from third countries (i.e. countries which are not Member States of the European Economic Area).				
	I do not agree	I agree	Neither nor	Hi-signif.*
Gender				,17
men	15,4	75,6	9	
women	15,1	71,2	13,6	
Education				,66
Primary or less	15	73,7	11,3	
Vocational/secondary	13,9	75,3	10,8	
Post-secondary, higher or more	18,6	68,9	12,6	
Age				,01
18-34 years	16,6	65,2	18,2	
35-54 years	15,4	74,8	9,8	
55 years and more	13,7	78,5	7,7	
Region				,94
Pomurska region	20,5	69,2	10,3	
Podravska region	12	79,6	8,3	
Koroška region	25	66,7	8,3	
Savinjska region	11,8	77,6	10,6	
Zasavska region	20	70	10	
Spodnje-posavska region	15,4	69,2	15,4	
South-eastern Slovenia	16,7	66,7	16,7	
Central Slovenia	17,6	70,5	11,9	
Gorenjska region	12,1	78,8	9,1	
Notranjsko-kraška region	11,8	70,6	17,6	
Goriška region	13,9	72,2	13,9	
Obalno-kraška region	13,9	77,8	8,3	
Total	15,2	73,5	11,3	

NOTE: differences are marked with various colours; green – data are statistically significantly higher regarding the entire population; grey – data are statistically significantly lower regarding the entire population

* Differences between groups are calculated according to the χ^2 method.

V. ATTACHMENTS

The table below displays results by socio-demographic categories.

Display: Percentage by socio-demographic categories

Genetically modified food offers the possibility of developing new, better food products.			
	Yes, it is true	No, it is not true	Hi-signif.*
Gender			,09
men	33,3	66,7	
women	26,9	73,1	
Education			,09
Primary or less	24,5	75,5	
Vocational/secondary	29	71	
Post-secondary, higher or more	36,7	63,3	
Age			,00
18-34 years	53,3	46,7	
35-54 years	24,4	75,6	
55 years and more	17,6	82,4	
Region			,79
Pomurska region	28,1	71,9	
Podravska region	36,4	63,6	
Koroška region	28,6	71,4	
Savinjska region	30,5	69,5	
Zasavska region	31,3	68,8	
Spodnje-posavska region	31,6	68,4	
South-eastern Slovenia	31	69	
Central Slovenia	28,7	71,3	
Gorenjska region	21,7	78,3	
Notranjsko-kraška region	42,9	57,1	
Goriška region	21,2	78,8	
Obalno-kraška region	38,9	61,1	
Total	30,2	69,8	

NOTE: differences are marked with various colours; green – data are statistically significantly higher regarding the entire population; grey – data are statistically significantly lower regarding the entire population

* Differences between groups are calculated according to the χ^2 method.

V. ATTACHMENTS

The table below displays results by socio-demographic categories.

Display: Percentage by socio-demographic categories

Genetically modified food poses a risk to human health.			
	Yes, it is true	No, it is not true	Hi-signif.*
Gender			,09
men	84,6	15,4	
women	88,9	11,1	
Education			,09
Primary or less	89,4	10,6	
Vocational/secondary	88	12	
Post-secondary, higher or more	81,8	18,2	
Age			,00
18-34 years	78	22	
35-54 years	89,2	10,8	
55 years and more	90,8	9,2	
Region			,94
Pomurska region	94,4	5,6	
Podravska region	85,1	14,9	
Koroška region	91,3	8,7	
Savinjska region	88	12	
Zasavska region	88,2	11,8	
Spodnjeposavska region	91,3	8,7	
South-eastern Slovenia	88,9	11,1	
Central Slovenia	85,1	14,9	
Gorenjska region	85,2	14,8	
Notranjsko-kraška region	87,5	12,5	
Goriška region	82,9	17,1	
Obalno-kraška region	86,1	13,9	
Total	86,8	13,2	

NOTE: differences are marked with various colours; green – data are statistically significantly higher regarding the entire population; grey – data are statistically significantly lower regarding the entire population

* Differences between groups are calculated according to the χ^2 method.

V. ATTACHMENTS

The table below displays results by socio-demographic categories.

Display: Percentage by socio-demographic categories

Genetically modified food is ethically acceptable.			
	Yes, it is true	No, it is not true	Hi-signif.*
Gender			,26
men	25,1	74,9	
women	21,2	78,8	
Education			,13
Primary or less	16,1	83,9	
Vocational/secondary	24,1	75,9	
Post-secondary, higher or more	26,1	73,9	
Age			,00
18-34 years	39,1	60,9	
35-54 years	20,7	79,3	
55 years and more	13,4	86,6	
Region			,17
Pomurska region	17,6	82,4	
Podravska region	26,2	73,8	
Koroška region	17,4	82,6	
Savinjska region	20	80	
Zasavska region	36,8	63,2	
Spodnjeposavska region	23,1	76,9	
South-eastern Slovenia	11,6	88,4	
Central Slovenia	23	77	
Gorenjska region	22,2	77,8	
Notranjsko-kraška region	47,1	52,9	
Goriška region	20,6	79,4	
Obalno-kraška region	32,4	67,6	
Total	23,2	76,8	

NOTE: differences are marked with various colours; green – data are statistically significantly higher regarding the entire population; grey – data are statistically significantly lower regarding the entire population

* Differences between groups are calculated according to the χ^2 method.

V. ATTACHMENTS

The table below displays results by socio-demographic categories.

Display: Percentage by socio-demographic categories

Food containing nano-ingredients offers the possibility of developing new, better food products.			
	Yes, it is true	No, it is not true	Hi-signif.*
Gender			,61
men	30,9	69,1	
women	28,3	71,7	
Education			,46
Primary or less	36,4	63,6	
Vocational/secondary	27,6	72,4	
Post-secondary, higher or more	31,2	68,8	
Age			,13
18-34 years	37,3	62,7	
35-54 years	26,2	73,8	
55 years and more	26,1	73,9	
Region			,16
Pomurska region	33,3	66,7	
Podravska region	45,3	54,7	
Koroška region	23,1	76,9	
Savinjska region	23,9	76,1	
Zasavska region	57,1	42,9	
Spodnjeposavska region	30,8	69,2	
South-eastern Slovenia	17,4	82,6	
Central Slovenia	24,1	75,9	
Gorenjska region	24,3	75,7	
Notranjsko-kraška region	20	80	
Goriška region	30,8	69,2	
Obalno-kraška region	28,6	71,4	
Total	29,6	70,4	

NOTE: differences are marked with various colours; green – data are statistically significantly higher regarding the entire population; grey – data are statistically significantly lower regarding the entire population

* Differences between groups are calculated according to the χ^2 method.

V. ATTACHMENTS

The table below displays results by socio-demographic categories.

Display: Percentage by socio-demographic categories

Food containing nano-ingredients poses risk to human health.		Yes, it is true	No, it is not true	Hi-signif.*
Gender				,56
men		80,5	19,5	
women		82,8	17,2	
Education				,54
Primary or less		77,1	22,9	
Vocational/secondary		83,5	16,5	
Post-secondary, higher or more		79,8	20,2	
Age				,01
18-34 years		73,9	26,1	
35-54 years		88,2	11,8	
55 years and more		80,6	19,4	
Region				,01
Pomurska region		93,8	6,3	
Podravska region		69,6	30,4	
Koroška region		58,3	41,7	
Savinjska region		90,6	9,4	
Zasavska region		71,4	28,6	
Spodnje-posavska region		87,5	12,5	
South-eastern Slovenia		100	0	
Central Slovenia		79,3	20,7	
Gorenjska region		85,7	14,3	
Notranjsko-kraška region		75	25	
Goriška region		78,6	21,4	
Obalno-kraška region		94,1	5,9	
Total		81,6	18,4	

NOTE: differences are marked with various colours; green – data are statistically significantly higher regarding the entire population; grey – data are statistically significantly lower regarding the entire population

* Differences between groups are calculated according to the χ^2 method.

V. ATTACHMENTS

The table below displays results by socio-demographic categories.

Display: Percentage by socio-demographic categories

Food containing nano-ingredients is ethically acceptable.			
	Yes, it is true	No, it is not true	Hi-signif.*
Gender			,95
men	23,3	76,7	
women	22,9	77,1	
Education			,04
Primary or less	10	90	
Vocational/secondary	23,2	76,8	
Post-secondary, higher or more	29,8	70,2	
Age			,00
18-34 years	40	60	
35-54 years	19,1	80,9	
55 years and more	11,6	88,4	
Region			,24
Pomurska region	27,8	72,2	
Podravska region	34,8	65,2	
Koroška region	8,3	91,7	
Savinjska region	16,3	83,7	
Zasavska region	50	50	
Spodnjeposavska region	20	80	
South-eastern Slovenia	9,1	90,9	
Central Slovenia	24,7	75,3	
Gorenjska region	16,2	83,8	
Notranjsko-kraška region	20	80	
Goriška region	38,5	61,5	
Obalno-kraška region	17,6	82,4	
Total	23,2	76,8	

NOTE: differences are marked with various colours; green – data are statistically significantly higher regarding the entire population; grey – data are statistically significantly lower regarding the entire population

* Differences between groups are calculated according to the χ^2 method.

V. ATTACHMENTS

The table below displays results by socio-demographic categories.

Display: Percentage by socio-demographic categories

Animal cloning for food products offers the possibility of developing new, better food products.

	Yes, it is true	No, it is not true	Hi-signif.*
Gender			,01
men	22,2	77,8	
women	14,1	85,9	
Education			,37
Primary or less	19	81	
Vocational/secondary	16,2	83,8	
Post-secondary, higher or more	21,2	78,8	
Age			,00
18-34 years	31,5	68,5	
35-54 years	14,2	85,8	
55 years and more	12,1	87,9	
Region			,34
Pomurska region	18,2	81,8	
Podravska region	25,2	74,8	
Koroška region	18,2	81,8	
Savinjska region	20,5	79,5	
Zasavska region	5,6	94,4	
Spodnje-posavska region	22,7	77,3	
South-eastern Slovenia	14	86	
Central Slovenia	14,6	85,4	
Gorenjska region	13,6	86,4	
Notranjsko-kraška region	33,3	66,7	
Goriška region	18,2	81,8	
Obalno-kraška region	21,9	78,1	
Total	18,1	81,9	

NOTE: differences are marked with various colours; green – data are statistically significantly higher regarding the entire population; grey – data are statistically significantly lower regarding the entire population

* Differences between groups are calculated according to the χ^2 method.

V. ATTACHMENTS

The table below displays results by socio-demographic categories.

Display: Percentage by socio-demographic categories

Animal cloning for food products poses a risk to human health.			
	Yes, it is true	No, it is not true	Hi-signif.*
Gender			,02
men	81,8	18,2	
women	88,7	11,3	
Education			,17
Primary or less	82,4	17,6	
Vocational/secondary	87,5	12,5	
Post-secondary, higher or more	81,9	18,1	
Age			,10
18-34 years	80,1	19,9	
35-54 years	86,8	13,2	
55 years and more	86,9	13,1	
Region			,83
Pomurska region	89,2	10,8	
Podravska region	87,7	12,3	
Koroška region	75	25	
Savinjska region	84,5	15,5	
Zasavska region	88,2	11,8	
Spodnje-posavska region	82,6	17,4	
South-eastern Slovenia	93,2	6,8	
Central Slovenia	82,5	17,5	
Gorenjska region	86,7	13,3	
Notranjsko-kraška region	81,3	18,8	
Goriška region	85,3	14,7	
Obalno-kraška region	90	10	
Total	85,1	14,9	

NOTE: differences are marked with various colours; green – data are statistically significantly higher regarding the entire population; grey – data are statistically significantly lower regarding the entire population

* Differences between groups are calculated according to the χ^2 method.

V. ATTACHMENTS

The table below displays results by socio-demographic categories.

Display: Percentage by socio-demographic categories

Animal cloning for food products is ethically acceptable.			
	Yes, it is true	No, it is not true	Hi-signif.*
Gender			,13
men	14,5	85,5	
women	10,7	89,3	
Education			,17
Primary or less	17,2	82,8	
Vocational/secondary	11,9	88,1	
Post-secondary, higher or more	10,1	89,9	
Age			,56
18-34 years	14,9	85,1	
35-54 years	11,3	88,7	
55 years and more	12,4	87,6	
Region			,05
Pomurska region	10,5	89,5	
Podravska region	20,4	79,6	
Koroška region	4,3	95,7	
Savinjska region	15,3	84,7	
Zasavska region	11,8	88,2	
Spodnje-posavska region	8,7	91,3	
South-eastern Slovenia	6,7	93,3	
Central Slovenia	8,2	91,8	
Gorenjska region	8,1	91,9	
Notranjsko-kraška region	18,8	81,3	
Goriška region	20	80	
Obalno-kraška region	22,9	77,1	
Total	12,7	87,3	

NOTE: differences are marked with various colours; green – data are statistically significantly higher regarding the entire population; grey – data are statistically significantly lower regarding the entire population

* Differences between groups are calculated according to the χ^2 method.

V. ATTACHMENTS

The table below displays results by socio-demographic categories.

Display: Percentage by socio-demographic categories

Are you familiar with, or have you heard of, the European Food Safety Authority, which was established in 2002?				
	Yes, I am familiar with it.	I have heard of it, but I am not familiar with its activities.	I am not familiar with it; I have never heard of it.	Hi-signif.*
Gender				,78
men	15,8	47,3	36,9	
women	14,2	47,4	38,4	
Education				,00
Primary or less	8,7	26,8	64,5	
Vocational/secondary	14	52,8	33,2	
Post-secondary, higher or more	22,5	51,5	26	
Age				,27
18-34 years	12,5	46,2	41,3	
35-54 years	15,9	51,3	32,9	
55 years and more	15,6	43,9	40,5	
Region				,74
Pomurska region	17,5	45	37,5	
Podravska region	12,5	52,7	34,8	
Koroška region	13	56,5	30,4	
Savinjska region	14,9	52,9	32,2	
Zasavska region	15	40	45	
Spodnjeposavska region	25,9	48,1	25,9	
South-eastern Slovenia	12,5	37,5	50	
Central Slovenia	17,2	45	37,8	
Gorenjska region	19,1	36,8	44,1	
Notranjsko-kraška region	11,1	50	38,9	
Goriška region	7,7	48,7	43,6	
Obalno-kraška region	10,3	56,4	33,3	
Total	15	47,4	37,7	

NOTE: differences are marked with various colours; green – data are statistically significantly higher regarding the entire population; grey – data are statistically significantly lower regarding the entire population

* Differences between groups are calculated according to the χ^2 method.

V. ATTACHMENTS

The table below displays results by socio-demographic categories.

Display: Percentage by socio-demographic categories; mean average by socio-demographic categories

To what extent do you trust consumer organisations' information about food safety and possible risks?								
	I do not trust at all	I do not trust	I neither trust nor distrust	I trust	I trust completely	Hi-signif.*	Mean average	Hi-signif.**
Gender						,64		,67
men	7,3	15	35,9	34,5	7,3		3,19	
women	5,5	17,4	38,1	33,4	5,5		3,16	
Education						,00		,00
Primary or less	4,3	23,9	50,7	17,4	3,6		2,93	
Vocational/secondary	7,4	15,2	35	36,3	6,1		3,18	
Post-secondary, higher or more	6,5	12,4	29,6	41,4	10,1		3,36	
Age						,50		,22
18-34 years	7,6	16,2	37,8	30,8	7,6		3,15	
35-54 years	5,4	14	35,6	39,2	5,8		3,25	
55 years and more	6,8	18,7	37,9	30,2	6,4		3,11	
Region						,50		,98
Pomurska region	0	27,5	47,5	25	0		2,97	
Podravska region	4,5	15,3	37,8	36	6,3		3,25	
Koroška region	12,5	8,3	33,3	33,3	12,5		3,25	
Savinjska region	5,7	19,5	34,5	35,6	4,6		3,14	
Zasavska region	15,8	15,8	21,1	42,1	5,3		3,08	
Spodnje-posavska region	7,7	15,4	42,3	23,1	11,5		3,1	
South-eastern Slovenia	4,1	16,3	36,7	42,9	0		3,22	
Central Slovenia	8,3	16	34,3	32,6	8,8		3,18	
Gorenjska region	5,9	14,7	36,8	35,3	7,4		3,22	
Notranjsko-kraška region	0	27,8	38,9	27,8	5,6		3,04	
Goriška region	2,6	15,8	42,1	34,2	5,3		3,21	
Obalno-kraška region	12,8	2,6	43,6	28,2	12,8		3,22	
Total	6,5	16,2	36,9	33,9	6,5		3,18	

NOTE: differences are marked with various colours; green – data are statistically significantly higher regarding the entire population; grey – data are statistically significantly lower regarding the entire population

* Differences between groups are calculated according to the χ^2 method.

** Differences between groups are calculated according to the ANOVA method.

V. ATTACHMENTS

The table below displays results by socio-demographic categories.

Display: Percentage by socio-demographic categories; mean average by socio-demographic categories

To what extent do you trust scientists' information about food safety and possible risks?								
	I do not trust at all	I do not trust	I neither trust nor distrust	I trust	I trust completely	Hi-signif.*	Mean average	Hi-signif.**
Gender						,16		,31
men	3,7	14,1	34,1	34,9	13,2		3,4	
women	2,3	10,4	35,1	42	10,1		3,47	
Education						,00		,00
Primary or less	1,5	24,1	43,8	27	3,6		3,07	
Vocational/secondary	3,3	10,4	33,1	39,7	13,5		3,5	
Post-secondary, higher or more	3,6	7,1	31	44,6	13,7		3,57	
Age						,00		,01
18-34 years	2,2	10,9	31,5	35,9	19,6		3,59	
35-54 years	3,9	8,6	36,6	41,2	9,7		3,44	
55 years and more	2,5	17,7	35	36,7	8		3,3	
Region						,75		,49
Pomurska region	0	7,5	45	35	12,5		3,51	
Podravska region	2,7	11,6	34,8	38,4	12,5		3,47	
Koroška region	8,7	13	39,1	39,1	0		3,1	
Savinjska region	3,4	16,1	33,3	32,2	14,9		3,41	
Zasavska region	0	0	40	40	20		3,76	
Spodnjeposavska region	4	12	20	56	8		3,5	
South-eastern Slovenia	2	14,3	34,7	42,9	6,1		3,38	
Central Slovenia	3,9	12,2	33,9	38,9	11,1		3,41	
Gorenjska region	1,5	13,2	29,4	42,6	13,2		3,54	
Notranjsko-kraška region	11,1	11,1	22,2	50	5,6		3,3	
Goriška region	5,1	15,4	41	33,3	5,1		3,21	
Obalno-kraška region	0	10,3	43,6	23,1	23,1		3,58	
Total	3	12,3	34,7	38,4	11,6		3,43	

NOTE: differences are marked with various colours; green – data are statistically significantly higher regarding the entire population; grey – data are statistically significantly lower regarding the entire population

* Differences between groups are calculated according to the χ^2 method.

** Differences between groups are calculated according to the ANOVA method.

V. ATTACHMENTS

The table below displays results by socio-demographic categories.

Display: Percentage by socio-demographic categories; mean average by socio-demographic categories

To what extent do you trust the European Food Safety Authority's information about food safety and possible risks?								
	I do not trust at all	I do not trust	I neither trust nor distrust	I trust	I trust completely	Hi-signif.*	Mean average	Hi-signif.**
Gender								
						,05		,53
men	6,7	15,2	33,4	36,5	8,1		3,24	
women	5,8	12,2	43,5	33,9	4,6		3,19	
Education								
						,00		,00
Primary or less	8,6	24,5	43,2	20,9	2,9		2,85	
Vocational/secondary	5,6	10,7	36,9	39,4	7,4		3,32	
Post-secondary, higher or more	6	11,9	38,1	36,9	7,1		3,27	
Age								
						,00		,00
18-34 years	3,2	10,2	32,3	42,5	11,8		3,5	
35-54 years	6,9	9,7	43,3	34,7	5,4		3,22	
55 years and more	8,4	21,1	37,6	29,5	3,4		2,99	
Region								
						,91		,49
Pomurska region	5	15	47,5	30	2,5		3,13	
Podravska region	6,3	11,6	36,6	39,3	6,3		3,27	
Koroška region	8,3	16,7	37,5	33,3	4,2		3,06	
Savinjska region	1,2	11,6	37,2	44,2	5,8		3,39	
Zasavska region	4,8	9,5	57,1	23,8	4,8		3,18	
Spodnjeposavska region	7,7	7,7	34,6	34,6	15,4		3,38	
South-eastern Slovenia	4,1	16,3	38,8	36,7	4,1		3,21	
Central Slovenia	10	15,6	38,3	28,3	7,8		3,07	
Gorenjska region	5,9	13,2	36,8	35,3	8,8		3,27	
Notranjsko-kraška region	5,6	11,1	38,9	44,4	0		3,12	
Goriška region	5,3	13,2	42,1	36,8	2,6		3,18	
Obalno-kraška region	2,6	15,4	30,8	43,6	7,7		3,39	
Total	6,3	13,7	38,5	35,2	6,4		3,22	

NOTE: differences are marked with various colours; green – data are statistically significantly higher regarding the entire population; grey – data are statistically significantly lower regarding the entire population

* Differences between groups are calculated according to the χ^2 method.

** Differences between groups are calculated according to the ANOVA method.

V. ATTACHMENTS

The table below displays results by socio-demographic categories.

Display: Percentage by socio-demographic categories; mean average by socio-demographic categories

To what extent do you trust state ministries' and inspection services' information about food safety and possible risks?								
	I do not trust at all	I do not trust	I neither trust nor distrust	I trust	I trust completely	Hi-signif.*	Mean average	Hi-signif.**
Gender						,11		,08
men	15,5	20,3	34,6	25,1	4,5		2,82	
women	9,8	21,7	34,1	30,9	3,5		2,97	
Education						,00		,00
Primary or less	14,6	32,8	32,8	17,5	2,2		2,6	
Vocational/secondary	11,5	17,8	36,6	28,8	5,3		2,99	
Post-secondary, higher or more	14,3	19	30,4	34,5	1,8		2,91	
Age						,00		,00
18-34 years	9,7	15,1	35,7	34,1	5,4		3,11	
35-54 years	15,1	18,7	31,3	31,3	3,6		2,9	
55 years and more	12,7	28,3	36,7	19,4	3		2,72	
Region						,05		,42
Pomurska region	12,5	30	30	25	2,5		2,73	
Podravska region	18	16,2	29,7	30,6	5,4		2,88	
Koroška region	20	28	28	24	0		2,56	
Savinjska region	3,4	21,8	39,1	35,6	0		3,08	
Zasavska region	15	20	25	35	5		2,99	
Spodnjeposavska region	30,8	19,2	26,9	15,4	7,7		2,58	
South-eastern Slovenia	14,6	16,7	29,2	39,6	0		2,92	
Central Slovenia	13,9	22,2	36,1	20	7,8		2,85	
Gorenjska region	8,7	17,4	34,8	36,2	2,9		3,07	
Notranjsko-kraška region	5,6	27,8	33,3	33,3	0		2,97	
Goriška region	12,8	20,5	43,6	23,1	0		2,79	
Obalno-kraška region	5,1	25,6	41	23,1	5,1		2,98	
Total	12,7	21	34,4	27,9	3,9		2,89	

NOTE: differences are marked with various colours; green – data are statistically significantly higher regarding the entire population; grey – data are statistically significantly lower regarding the entire population

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** Differences between groups are calculated according to the ANOVA method.

V. ATTACHMENTS

The table below displays results by socio-demographic categories.

Display: Percentage by socio-demographic categories; mean average by socio-demographic categories

To what extent do you trust information from the media about food safety and possible risks?								
	I do not trust at all	I do not trust	I neither trust nor distrust	I trust	I trust completely	Hi-signif.*	Mean average	Hi-signif.**
Gender						,02		,01
men	19,4	30,7	33,8	14,9	1,1		2,47	
women	11,6	28,4	42,9	15,9	1,2		2,66	
Education						,09		,15
Primary or less	10,9	31,4	36,5	20,4	0,7		2,69	
Vocational/secondary	17,3	26,2	41	14	1,5		2,56	
Post-secondary, higher or more	15,4	36,7	33,7	14,2	0		2,47	
Age						,06		,00
18-34 years	19,5	34,1	36,8	9,7	0		2,36	
35-54 years	15,9	28,5	38,3	15,9	1,4		2,59	
55 years and more	11,9	27,7	40	19,1	1,3		2,7	
Region						,55		,14
Pomurska region	20	25	35	17,5	2,5		2,57	
Podravska region	17,1	30,6	30,6	19,8	1,8		2,57	
Koroška region	8,3	20,8	33,3	33,3	4,2		3,09	
Savinjska region	10,3	25,3	40,2	23	1,1		2,8	
Zasavska region	15	35	45	5	0		2,42	
Spodnje-posavska region	26,9	23,1	30,8	19,2	0		2,48	
South-eastern Slovenia	13	39,1	39,1	8,7	0		2,46	
Central Slovenia	17,8	29,4	40	12,2	0,6		2,47	
Gorenjska region	14,7	35,3	38,2	10,3	1,5		2,48	
Notranjsko-kraška region	17,6	29,4	41,2	11,8	0		2,49	
Goriška region	10,3	35,9	46,2	7,7	0		2,54	
Obalno-kraška region	12,8	25,6	46,2	15,4	0		2,65	
Total	15,6	29,7	38,3	15,4	1,1		2,57	

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** Differences between groups are calculated according to the ANOVA method.

V. ATTACHMENTS

The table below displays results by socio-demographic categories.

Display: Percentage by socio-demographic categories; mean average by socio-demographic categories

To what extent do you trust the food industry's information about food safety and possible risks?								
	I do not trust at all	I do not trust	I neither trust nor distrust	I trust	I trust completely	Hi-signif.*	Mean average	Hi-signif.**
Gender						,01		,00
men	15,5	33,2	35,2	14,6	1,4		2,53	
women	9,3	28,8	41,6	20,1	0,3		2,73	
Education						,01		,00
Primary or less	6,5	29,7	39,9	23,9	0		2,8	
Vocational/secondary	11,2	31	39,4	17	1,3		2,66	
Post-secondary, higher or more	20,1	31,4	34,9	13	0,6		2,43	
Age						,41		,58
18-34 years	11,9	27,6	40,5	20	0		2,68	
35-54 years	13,3	32,6	37,6	14,7	1,8		2,59	
55 years and more	12,2	31,5	37,4	18,5	0,4		2,64	
Region						,78		,50
Pomurska region	7,3	34,1	43,9	14,6	0		2,68	
Podravska region	14,4	27	38,7	18,9	0,9		2,65	
Koroška region	12,5	29,2	45,8	12,5	0		2,62	
Savinjska region	8	36,8	35,6	18,4	1,1		2,67	
Zasavska region	10	20	35	30	5		3,07	
Spodnjeposavska region	15,4	23,1	34,6	23,1	3,8		2,79	
South-eastern Slovenia	16,7	29,2	37,5	16,7	0		2,56	
Central Slovenia	15,1	31,8	36,3	16,8	0		2,54	
Gorenjska region	7,4	29,4	45,6	16,2	1,5		2,76	
Notranjsko-kraška region	11,1	27,8	50	11,1	0		2,6	
Goriška region	10,3	38,5	35,9	15,4	0		2,57	
Obalno-kraška region	17,9	35,9	30,8	15,4	0		2,45	
Total	12,5	31	38,4	17,4	0,8		2,63	

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** Differences between groups are calculated according to the ANOVA method.

V. ATTACHMENTS

The table below displays results by socio-demographic categories.

Display: Percentage by socio-demographic categories; mean average by socio-demographic categories

To what extent does the European Food Safety Authority and its activities contribute to providing food safety?								
	It does not contribute at all	It does not contribute	Neither contributes nor does not contribute	It contributes	It contributes significantly	Hi-signif.*	Mean average	Hi-signif.**
Gender						,81		,66
men	3,1	11,8	42,4	37,9	4,8		3,29	
women	4,1	9,9	45,8	36,2	4,1		3,26	
Education						,02		,00
Primary or less	4,3	12,3	55,8	27,5	0		3,07	
Vocational/secondary	3,8	10,4	40,5	39,9	5,3		3,32	
Post-secondary, higher or more	2,4	10,7	42,6	38,5	5,9		3,35	
Age						,00		,00
18-34 years	2,2	8,6	33,5	48,6	7		3,49	
35-54 years	4	10,1	45,5	36,1	4,3		3,26	
55 years and more	3,8	13,5	50,6	29,5	2,5		3,13	
Region						,13		,08
Pomurska region	0	7,7	64,1	25,6	2,6		3,21	
Podravska region	3,6	15,2	35,7	39,3	6,3		3,31	
Koroška region	0	29,2	37,5	29,2	4,2		3,05	
Savinjska region	1,1	8	36,8	49,4	4,6		3,48	
Zasavska region	0	5	40	45	10		3,58	
Spodnje-posavska region	3,8	7,7	38,5	38,5	11,5		3,51	
South-eastern Slovenia	2,1	8,3	45,8	41,7	2,1		3,35	
Central Slovenia	7,2	12,2	45	32,2	3,3		3,13	
Gorenjska region	4,5	9	44,8	35,8	6		3,28	
Notranjsko-kraška region	5,6	11,1	44,4	38,9	0		3,15	
Goriška region	0	10,5	50	36,8	2,6		3,33	
Obalno-kraška region	2,6	2,6	59	35,9	0		3,28	
Total	3,6	10,8	44,1	37,1	4,4		3,28	

NOTE: differences are marked with various colours; green – data are statistically significantly higher regarding the entire population; grey – data are statistically significantly lower according to the χ^2 method.

** Differences between groups are calculated according to the ANOVA method.

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V. ATTACHMENTS

The table below displays results by socio-demographic categories.

Display: Percentage by socio-demographic categories; mean average by socio-demographic categories

To what extent does the European Union and its acts on food safety contribute to providing food safety?								
	It does not contribute at all	It does not contribute	Neither contributes nor does not contribute	It contributes	It contributes significantly	Hi-signif.*	Mean average	Hi-signif.**
Gender						,90		,82
men	3,9	13,2	38	40,3	4,5		3,29	
women	3,2	13	41,7	37,7	4,3		3,27	
Education						,03		,01
Primary or less	6,5	19,6	35,5	37,7	0,7		3,06	
Vocational/secondary	2,5	11,5	40,7	39,2	6,1		3,35	
Post-secondary, higher or more	3,6	11,2	41,4	39,6	4,1		3,3	
Age						,00		,00
18-34 years	1,1	7,6	34,6	47	9,7		3,57	
35-54 years	3,6	11,9	42,8	38,5	3,2		3,25	
55 years and more	5,5	19	40,1	33,3	2,1		3,07	
Region						,58		,53
Pomurska region	0	22,5	30	45	2,5		3,29	
Podravska region	4,5	17,1	34,2	36,9	7,2		3,26	
Koroška region	4,2	25	37,5	33,3	0		2,99	
Savinjska region	3,4	10,3	33,3	50,6	2,3		3,39	
Zasavska region	0	15	40	40	5		3,39	
Spodnje-posavska region	0	15,4	26,9	53,8	3,8		3,47	
South-eastern Slovenia	2,1	6,3	45,8	41,7	4,2		3,43	
Central Slovenia	6,6	11,6	43,1	35,4	3,3		3,18	
Gorenjska region	4,4	13,2	42,6	33,8	5,9		3,24	
Notranjsko-kraška region	5,9	5,9	47,1	41,2	0		3,25	
Goriška region	0	10,5	47,4	34,2	7,9		3,37	
Obalno-kraška region	0	10,3	51,3	33,3	5,1		3,33	
Total	3,6	13	39,8	38,9	4,5		3,28	

NOTE: differences are marked with various colours; green – data are statistically significantly higher regarding the entire population; grey – data are statistically significantly lower regarding the entire population

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** Differences between groups are calculated according to the ANOVA method.

V. ATTACHMENTS

The table below displays results by socio-demographic categories.

Display: Percentage by socio-demographic categories; mean average by socio-demographic categories

To what extent does the work of Slovenian ministries and inspection services contribute to providing food safety?								
	It does not contribute at all	It does not contribute	Neither contributes nor does not contribute	It contributes	It contributes significantly	Hi-signif.*	Mean average	Hi-signif.**
Gender						,63		,69
men	9,6	21,7	35,2	31,5	2		2,94	
women	9	21,4	40	28,7	0,9		2,91	
Education						,30		,02
Primary or less	13,1	24,1	40,9	21,2	0,7		2,73	
Vocational/secondary	8,7	20,9	37,8	31,1	1,5		2,96	
Post-secondary, higher or more	7,7	20,7	34,9	34,9	1,8		3,02	
Age						,15		,18
18-34 years	7,6	17,3	44,3	29,2	1,6		3	
35-54 years	10,4	19,1	35,6	33,1	1,8		2,96	
55 years and more	9,3	27,4	34,6	27,4	1,3		2,83	
Region						,70		,44
Pomurska region	15,4	35,9	25,6	23,1	0		2,57	
Podravska region	16,4	16,4	34,5	30	2,7		2,86	
Koroška region	16,7	16,7	33,3	33,3	0		2,84	
Savinjska region	5,7	23,9	37,5	31,8	1,1		2,99	
Zasavska region	5,3	15,8	26,3	52,6	0		3,21	
Spodnje-posavska region	7,7	19,2	42,3	30,8	0		2,92	
South-eastern Slovenia	10,4	14,6	43,8	29,2	2,1		2,96	
Central Slovenia	6,6	21,5	39,8	29,8	2,2		3	
Gorenjska region	9	25,4	35,8	28,4	1,5		2,89	
Notranjsko-kraška region	16,7	22,2	33,3	27,8	0		2,72	
Goriška region	7,7	17,9	48,7	25,6	0		2,93	
Obalno-kraška region	0	25,6	41	33,3	0		3,07	
Total	9,3	21,5	37,6	30,1	1,5		2,93	

NOTE: differences are marked with various colours; green – data are statistically significantly higher regarding the entire population; grey – data are statistically significantly lower regarding the entire population

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** Differences between groups are calculated according to the ANOVA method.

V. ATTACHMENTS

The table below displays results by socio-demographic categories.

Display: Percentage by socio-demographic categories; mean average by socio-demographic categories

To what extent does the work of non-governmental organisations contribute to providing food safety?								
	It does not contribute at all	It does not contribute	Neither contributes nor does not contribute	It contributes	It contributes significantly	Hi-signif.*	Mean average	Hi-signif.**
Gender						,40		,18
men	3,4	12,4	36,4	40,4	7,3		3,36	
women	2,6	14,2	41,2	37,1	4,9		3,27	
Education						,11		,05
Primary or less	3,6	13	47,1	34,1	2,2		3,18	
Vocational/secondary	2,8	15	35,9	39,9	6,4		3,32	
Post-secondary, higher or more	3	9,5	39,1	39,6	8,9		3,43	
Age						,01		,00
18-34 years	1,1	15,7	39,5	35,7	8,1		3,34	
35-54 years	2,2	9,7	37,1	44,2	6,8		3,44	
55 years and more	5,9	15,2	40,1	34,6	4,2		3,16	
Region						,60		,73
Pomurska region	2,6	10,3	33,3	46,2	7,7		3,44	
Podravska region	6,4	13,6	30	40,9	9,1		3,33	
Koroška region	0	12,5	41,7	41,7	4,2		3,38	
Savinjska region	2,3	10,3	42,5	40,2	4,6		3,34	
Zasavska region	0	15	40	45	0		3,3	
Spodnje-posavska region	0	7,7	38,5	50	3,8		3,47	
South-eastern Slovenia	6,1	14,3	38,8	38,8	2		3,19	
Central Slovenia	3,9	14,5	38	36,9	6,7		3,27	
Gorenjska region	1,5	13,4	47,8	37,3	0		3,2	
Notranjsko-kraška region	0	11,8	52,9	35,3	0		3,28	
Goriška region	0	20	40	30	10		3,31	
Obalno-kraška region	0	10,3	38,5	33,3	17,9		3,59	
Total	3,1	13,2	38,8	38,7	6,2		3,32	

NOTE: differences are marked with various colours; green – data are statistically significantly higher regarding the entire population; grey – data are statistically significantly lower regarding the entire population

* Differences between groups are calculated according to the χ^2 method.

** Differences between groups are calculated according to the ANOVA method.

ARAGON | =

**Public opinion survey on risks relating to food,
and the recognisability of the European Food
Safety Authority in Slovenia**

Questionnaire

Hello, my name is (show name and surname) and I am calling from the company Aragon, d.o.o. We would like to ask you some questions about risks relating to food and familiarity with the European Food Safety Authority. May we take a few minutes of your time?

→ Food safety

Q1 Can you first tell us whether you trust safe food supplies, i.e. do you believe that the food you buy is safe?

Instructions for interviewers: Read out the ranking, one answer.

1. I do not trust at all
2. I do not trust
3. I neither trust nor distrust
4. I trust
5. I trust completely

Q2 Where do you obtain or find information about food safety?

Instructions for programming: Open-ended question

Instructions for interviewers: Encourage, ask additional questions, write down literal statements.

Q3 In your opinion, which foodstuffs that you consume pose the greatest health risk?

Instructions for programming: Open-ended question

Instructions for interviewers: Encourage, ask additional questions, write down literal statements.

- I do not know/I do not wish to answer/no answer

Q4 Why do you think these foodstuffs pose a risk to your health?

Instructions for programming: Open-ended question. If answer to Q3 is 'I do not know', skip this question.

Instructions for interviewers: Encourage, ask additional questions, write down literal statements.

Q5 In the next part, we would like to know how concerned you are about food safety. Please state for each of the following things whether it concerns you very much, quite or does not concern you.

Are you very concerned, quite concerned or not concerned about _____ (display element)?

Instructions for interviewers: Read each statement and mark one answer for each statement. If necessary, repeat the ranking for every statement.

Instructions for programming: Display elements in random order.

	I am very concerned	I am quite concerned	I am not concerned	I do not know
Food quality and freshness	1	2	3	4
Additives such as colour additives, preservatives or flavour intensifiers added to food and beverages	1	2	3	4
Pesticide residues in fruit, vegetables and cereals	1	2	3	4
Genetically modified food	1	2	3	4

V. ATTACHMENTS

Questionnaire

Animal cloning for food products	1	2	3	4
Nano-ingredients in food	1		3	4
Contaminants in foodstuffs (e.g. mercury in fish)	1	2	3	4
Veterinary drug residues (antibiotics, hormones) in meat	1	2	3	4
Food poisoning caused by the presence of bacteria (e.g. salmonella in eggs)	1	2	3	4
Allergic reactions to food/drinks	1	2	3	4

q8 We will read some statements now and we ask you to give your opinion on whether you think the statements are true or false.

Instructions for interviewers: Mark one answer for every statement.

Instructions for programming: Display sections A–C in random order.

A. q8a First, think about GENETICALLY MODIFIED FOOD and tell us whether the statements provided are true or false in your opinion.

Instructions for programming: Display statements in random order.

	Yes	No	I do not know
Genetically modified food offers the possibility of developing new, better food products.	1	2	3
Genetically modified food poses a risk to human health.	1	2	3
Genetically modified food is ethically acceptable.	1	2	3

B. q8b Now think about FOOD CONTAINING NANO-INGREDIENTS and tell us whether the statements provided are true or false in your opinion.

Instructions for programming: Display statements in random order.

	Yes	No	I do not know
Food containing nano-ingredients offers the possibility of developing new, better food products.	1	2	3
Food containing nano-ingredients poses a risk to human health.	1	2	3
Food containing nano-ingredients is ethically acceptable.	1	2	3

C. q8c Now think about ANIMAL CLONING FOR FOOD PRODUCTS and tell us whether the statements provided are true or false in your opinion.

Instructions for programming: Display statements in random order.

	Yes	No	I do not know
Animal cloning for food products offers the possibility of developing new, better food products.	1	2	3
Animal cloning for food products poses a risk to human health.	1	2	3
Animal cloning for food products is ethically acceptable.	1	2	3

3

V. ATTACHMENTS

Questionnaire

→ European Food Safety Authority

a7 Are you familiar with, or have you heard of, the European Food Safety Authority, which was established in 2002?

Instructions for interviewers: read the ranking, one answer.

1. Yes, I am familiar with it.
2. I have heard of it, but I am not familiar with its activities.
3. I am not familiar with it; I have never heard of it.

a8 We will read to you various sources. Please assess the level of TRUST you have in each source for obtaining information about food safety and possible risks. Use the scale from 1 to 5, where 1 means that you do not trust the source of information on food safety and 5 means that you completely trust the source. You are also free to give scores from 2 to 4.

To what extent do you trust information from _____ (display source) about food safety and possible risks?

Instructions for interviewers: mark one answer for each source.

Instructions for programming: Display sources in random order.

	1 - I do not trust at all	2 - I do not trust	3 - Neither nor	4 - I trust	5 - I trust completely
CONSUMER ORGANISATIONS	1	2	3	4	5
SCIENTISTS	1	2	3	4	5
EUROPEAN FOOD SAFETY AUTHORITY	1	2	3	4	5
STATE MINISTRIES AND INSPECTION SERVICES	1	2	3	4	5
MEDIA	1	2	3	4	5
FOOD INDUSTRY	1	2	3	4	5

a9 We will read to you the names of various institutions or organisations and we ask you to assess how much they contribute with their work to providing food safety in your opinion. Use the scale from 1 to 5, where 1 means that they do not contribute at all and 5 means that they contribute significantly to providing food safety.

To what extent do/does _____ (display element) contribute to providing food safety?

Instructions for interviewers: mark one answer for every statement.

Instructions for programming: Display elements in random order.

	1 - It does not contribute at all	2 - It does not contribute	3 - Neither nor	4 - It contributes	5 - It contributes significantly
Activities of the European Food Safety Authority	1	2	3	4	5
Acts of the European Union on food safety	1	2	3	4	5
Work of Slovenian ministries and inspection services	1	2	3	4	5
Activities of non-governmental organisations	1	2	3	4	5

V. ATTACHMENTS

Questionnaire

Q10 We will read to you several statements regarding safe food supply. Please respond to each statement with I agree or I do not agree.

Do you agree with the statement: _____

Instructions for interviewers: mark one answer for every statement.

Instructions for programming: Display elements in random order.

	I do not agree	I agree	Neither nor	I do not know
The food we consume now is safer than it was in the past.	1	2	3	4
In the field of food, the advantages of using new technologies and globalisation are greater than the risks.	1	2	3	4
A product label is the source of all the information I need about a foodstuff.	1	2	3	4
Food produced in the EU is safer than food imported from third countries (i.e. countries which are not Member States of the European Economic Area).	1	2	3	4

DEMOGRAPHY

D1 Gender:

Instructions for interviewers: Mark one answer (do not ask)

1. Man
2. Woman

D2 Age:

Instructions for interviewers: Write down the answer.

D3 Education:

Instructions for interviewers: Mark one answer (do not ask)

1. Graduated/not graduated from primary school
2. Two- or three-year secondary school
3. Four- or five-year secondary school
4. Higher or university education
5. Master's degree, specialisation, doctor's degree etc.
6. I do not want to answer

D4 Region:

Instructions for interviewers: Mark one answer (do not ask)

- 1 Pomurska region
- 2 Podravska region
- 3 Koroska region
- 4 Savinjska region
- 5 Zasavska region

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V. ATTACHMENTS

Questionnaire

- 6 Spodnjeposavska region
- 7 South-eastern Slovenia
- 8 Central Slovenia
- 9 Gorenjska region
- 10 Notranjsko-kraška region
- 11 Goriška region
- 12 Obalno-kraška region

→ THANK YOU